

Rebuttal to “Comments on LNK1134 [↗](#) and LPK1133 [↗](#)”

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1. Point-by-point rebuttal of the Reply

In the following, all text that appears in quoted italics is a statement from the Reply by M. Oberlack and S. Hoyas. The text in normal font is our response. The points are not sorted by relevance, but are picked up as they appear when reading the Reply. In Section 2, we will list all critical points of our Comment that were not addressed in the Reply.

1. *“First, symmetry-based solutions are exact so-called invariant solutions of a given set of PDEs - here the multi-point moment equations, which are based on the instantaneous velocities. This is in perfect analogy e.g. to the Blasius solution, which is a solution of Prandtl’s boundary layer equation.”*

This statement is clearly misleading. The laminar case cannot be compared with the turbulent case. The mentioned Blasius solution emerges as an invariant solution for *laminar flow*, where all equations are closed. In such cases, Lie-group symmetry analysis works well, since solutions get mapped to solutions. For unclosed equations, however, as in turbulence, this does not hold anymore, and the authors should know it.

Anyone with a bit of experience in Lie-group symmetry analysis knows the basic fact that for unclosed systems the strong concept of symmetry turns into the weaker concept of equivalence. That means, solutions are not necessarily mapped to solutions anymore. This is also true for unclosed systems that are formulated as an infinite chain of equations, as in turbulence. In particular, when correctly performing a Lie-group symmetry analysis on such an infinite chain of equations, it always will result to an infinite dimensional Lie-algebra. That means, the original closure problem of equations only shifts to a closure problem of symmetries. This leads to the massive problem that there is an infinite pool of symmetries to choose from, and if no modelling is involved, as in [1], then there is a high chance that nonphysical symmetries will be chosen which are not reflected by experiment or numerical simulation [2]. And exactly this is the case in [1], for the two “statistical symmetries” (8) & (9).

2. *“From the viewpoint of engineering fluid mechanics, which is strongly influenced by Reynolds’ decomposition, it seems unusual that we consider moment equations based on instantaneous velocities.”*

No, it does not. It all depends upon what flow properties are being studied and what flow quantities one ultimately wants to predict. For example, if one intends to make statements and draw conclusions about intermittency in a flow with a strong mean velocity, at which [1] aims at, then it is indeed unusual not to use Reynolds’ decomposition and not to subtract the mean flow from the measuring correlations. It is a mistake here not to separate the fluctuations from the mean flow, and if one decides to ignore this recommendation from Reynolds anyway, then one should not be surprised in the end when the results will lead to empty conclusions, as clearly shown in both Comments by Brethouwer and Frewer & Khujadze. And this fact is independent of whether one operates in the engineering, physics or mathematics community.

3. *“However, all other complete descriptions of turbulence, i.e. Lundgren’s hierarchies for the probability density function (PDF), the characteristic function equations or Hopf’s functional equation are based on instantaneous velocities.”*

This statement already makes clear that the authors do not understand, or do not want to understand, to which elements and steps of their scaling approach our critique is directed at. Our objection is not that instantaneous velocity equations get formulated. We do not criticize the formulation of equation (4) in [1]. It’s a valid equation and solutions can be sought. What we criticize is the misleading and incorrect interpretation of those solutions in [1] and the negligence of not checking whether these solutions are just mathematical artefacts or real solutions that can be matched to turbulence-relevant data. Because, if the authors would have checked their “solutions” properly, they would have immediately recognized that their “solution” approach in [1] is invalid. This is exactly what we did in our Comment, by pointing out the severe mismatch of their solutions in Fig. 1(c)-(d), but which the authors persistently look away from by not addressing this crucial point in their Reply.

4. *“Also, it should be noted that multi-point momentum equations based on instantaneous velocities are conservation laws. ... This is not true for equations based on fluctuations such as the Reynolds transport equations. These have highly complex source and sink terms and elementary invariant solutions do not exist.”*

Also this statement is misleading. Because between the instantaneous and the fluctuation moments there is a unique relationship (explicitly given by equation (1) in Brethouwer’s Comment), which allows to simply change between these two representations. That means, both representations are equivalent: If a solution is known in one representation, then it is also known in the other representation — it’s the same solution only represented differently. The same is also true for invariant transformations.

Sure, to search for invariances in the instantaneous approach is technically easier than in the fluctuation approach, since the equations can be written in a conservative form. And, if the equations were closed, then this instantaneous approach would be the preferable one to use. But, since the equations are unclosed (even when formally considering the entire infinite chain of moment equations, the system remains unclosed), the instantaneous approach has a decisive drawback when searching for physical and realizable invariances, as is thoroughly discussed in [3]. The problem lies in its linearity, because it amplifies the closure problem when applying a Lie-group invariance analysis to it. It’s the unpleasant effect of the linear superposition principle which adds an additional infinite dimension to the already infinite dimensional Lie-algebra of equivalence transformations that already results from the unclosedness of the equations themselves.

In other words, the problem of the instantaneous approach is that it hides the nonlinear information. In contrast of course to the fluctuation approach, which explicitly reveals the statistical nonlinearity and its different order-coupling between the moments. As we have shown in [3], this extra information provided by the fluctuation approach can be crucial for a Lie-group invariance analysis. For instance, it can detect nonphysical invariances, that is, invariant transformations which are not reflected by numerical or experimental data can be more easily and systematically detected in the nonlinear fluctuation approach than in the linear instantaneous approach.

And exactly this is the problem of the invariance analysis proposed in [1]. Without any analytical effort, the instantaneous approach immediately leads to the invariances (8) and (9) in [1], as they can be directly read off from the infinite and unclosed instantaneous equation (4). But by closer inspection, which the authors failed to do, these invariances reveal themselves only as mathematical artefacts. Would the authors have used the fluctuation

approach, they would have instantly seen that these two invariances are nonphysical and that they need to be discarded.

The claimed invariant solutions in [1] are ultimately no solutions. Because, if one would have a solution in the instantaneous representation, then one would automatically have the corresponding solution in the fluctuation representation too, as mentioned above due to the unique map between them. But this is not the case, as clearly shown in our Comment by Fig. 1(c)-(d): The mapped solutions cannot be matched to the data at all anymore, and, hence, cannot be solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations. A conclusion that can be clearly drawn, since this mismatch problem is structural and not a convergence issue of the data or a numerical stability issue of the fitting procedure [2, 3].

5. *“The naming to the latter symmetries were not coined in the PRL paper, but go back to the work of [4]. ... It requires transformation to the PDF image and that is exactly what has been done in the above paper [4] and then the name also emerges as an entirely meaningful description.”*

The mentioned paper “[4]” from 2014, on which the authors heavily rely on, is both methodologically and technically flawed, as was proven in [4–8]. That Oberlack’s symmetries (8) and (9) in [1] reflect non-Gaussianity and intermittency of turbulence, is of course plain fantasy. Their statement that one needs the PDF description of his symmetries to observe these properties is simply not true. His symmetries clearly violate basic constraints of the PDF equations, as we first proved in [4], but which Oberlack downplayed and misrepresented in his subsequent Reply [9]. This we clarified in [5–8], which additionally revealed that their paper “[4]” is technically flawed in many other respects as well. Unfortunately, for the journal the case was closed due to their publication policies, so we could not write a follow-up comment to point out all the other flaws that “[4]” has.

As an aside, it should be noted that as in “[4]”, where out of 6 authors of the original article only 2 eventually participated in the Reply [9], here again only 2 authors participate in the current Reply, although the original article [1] lists 5 authors. Is it because the authors who do not participate anymore all distance themselves from their original work?

6. *“First of all, it is common and purposeful to approximate a given solution by a set of other functions. This is exactly what has been done here and is in principle comparable to classical approximations e.g. of the Blasius solution. Brethouwer’s [sic] approximation for the turbulent scaling law under consideration seems to work OK and this is also true for the deficit law. However, one must be very careful with the evaluation, because if the approximation were really good, then the closure problem would hardly exist any more and, as is well known, this is not the case.”*

It is obvious that this combined statement is a clear misrepresentation of Brethouwer’s Comment. What Brethouwer shows is that a scaling law for the instantaneous velocity correlation of order $n = 3$ to 6 cannot probe the data deeper than up to second order in the fluctuation moments, due to the overwhelming dominance of the mean velocity field in the flow regions considered. In other words, the scaling laws in [1] are not sensitive enough to detect non-Gaussianity and intermittency in the data. Hence, the underlying symmetries in [1] “neither reflect the non-Gaussianity and intermittency of wall-bounded turbulent flows nor put new constraints on turbulence models”, as correctly concluded by Brethouwer.

What we also show in our Comment then even goes one step further. Our Figs. 1(c)-(d) additionally show that the derived scaling laws for the instantaneous velocity moments in [1] are not even solutions. Because, when re-writing them into the equivalent representation of the moment fluctuations, a severe systematic mismatch to the data arises, as shown by the red lines in our Figs. 1(c)-(d), but which were ignored and not commented on by Oberlack.

7. “But there is another problem with Brethouwer’s [sic] approximation, namely it is not new at all, Frewer has uploaded something similar to arXiv, and more than that, it has been proposed many times over the years by various colleagues at the different meetings where we presented our work - in short, all this here is not new.”

If our criticism is not new for the authors and has been known all along, then it makes the situation even worse. Does this show that the authors are not competent enough to understand their errors?

8. “However, we would like to demonstrate that the scaling laws are also valid for velocities which do not contain a mean velocity, namely here for U_2 and U_3 The above laws [(1)] with exactly the same numbers for the exponents, i.e. $\sigma_1 = 1.95$ and $\sigma_2 = 1.94$, are compared with the DNS data in Figure 1. The agreement speaks for itself, but fluctuations due to insufficient convergence are visible.”

What is shown in Figure 1 in the Reply, the so-called parallel-lines figure, is highly trivial and does not prove anything that their symmetry-based scaling approach works. This fact we have established by Fig. 1(a) in our Comment and, as referenced, explained in detail in Section 2 in [2]. There are three options here: Either the authors did not read our Comment carefully enough, or they ignored this simple fact, or they simply do not want to understand it.

To note here is that their argumentation for Figure 1 in the Reply is taken from slide 59 from Oberlack’s recent INI-seminar [☞](#), which has already been refuted in [10], and which we want to repeat here for clarity and completeness again.

Refuting the reasoning behind Figure 1, the so-called parallel-lines figure:

The results shown in Figure 1 in the Reply are highly trivial and do not prove anything that their symmetry-based scaling approach in [1] works. Firstly, that the two scaling exponents σ_1 and σ_2 are almost the same and close to 2 has nothing to do with “intermittent scaling”, as claimed in [1]. It only reflects the trivial fact that all even moments of U_2 and U_3 have a non-zero local extremum at channel center, like U_1 . And since these local extrema all start off quadratically, it is not surprising that we get a quadratic power-law scaling $(x_2/h)^2$ for all those moments close to channel center. Sure, the further away we move from channel center, the less it will be a pure quadratic scaling, since the higher-order Taylor terms slowly start to get relevant.

Secondly, as was already explained in Section 2 in [2] (see footnote 2) and illustratively shown for laminar flow in Fig. 1(a) in our Comment, this structure of parallel lines in a log-log-plot with a constant slope can be trivially achieved with any function $f(x)$ which is non-zero at $x = 0$ (when presented in deficit form). See Fig. 1 on the next page, where for example $f(x) = \cos(x)$ and its powers in deficit form up to order 6 is shown. With a suitable scaling, the curves can additionally either be evenly distributed or made to collapse. Close to $x = 0$, the slope is 2, since the cos-function starts off with a quadratic extremum.

In Fig. 2 below, the case $f(x) = \sin(x)$ is shown, which does not allow for such a structure of parallel lines as before, simply because $f(x)$ is zero at $x = 0$. In Fig. 3, however, the shifted case $f(x) = \sin(x)+1$ is shown, which works again. The slope close to $x = 0$ is now of course 1, since the sin-function starts off linearly.

Figure 1: $c_n|f(x)^n - f(0)^n|$, $n = 1, \dots, 6$ (from bottom to top), for $f(x) = \cos(x)$ and normalization $c_n = 1$ (a), $c_n = 2^n/n$ (b), $c_n = 16^n/n$ (c), $c_n = 2/n$ (d).

Figure 2: $|f(x)^n - f(0)^n|$, $n = 1, \dots, 6$ (from top to bottom), for $f(x) = \sin(x)$.

Figure 3: $c_n|f(x)^n - f(0)^n|$, $n = 1, \dots, 6$ (from bottom to top), for $f(x) = \sin(x)+1$ and normalization $c_n = 1$ (a), $c_n = 2^n/n$ (b), $c_n = 16^n/n$ (c), $c_n = 2/n$ (d).

Thirdly, that the authors only show the diagonal moments in Figure 1 in the Reply, and not the off-diagonal ones, is also clear now. Because, if they would show for example $\overline{U_1^n U_2}$, where their scaling law will again be the same as for any other moment (since their scaling is always isotropic), it will fail. Why? Because, since in channel flow we have the relation $\overline{U_1^n U_2} = \overline{u_1^n u_2} + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{k} \overline{U_1^k} \overline{u_1^{n-k} u_2}$, they are simply zero at channel center (as $\overline{u_1^n u_2}$ are all odd functions), which means that a structure of parallel lines does not exist for this case (analogous to what is shown in Fig. 2), and therefore cannot be “predicted” by their scaling theory, although it should, according to them, but in reality it does not.

Hence, what is shown in Figure 1 in the Reply is just trivial Taylor asymptotics around channel center, and not some special turbulent flow property. That the scaling is quadratic close to channel center and universal (parallel) for all moments shown is therefore trivial to predict. A sophisticated scaling theory is not needed — and if one nevertheless still likes to formulate this trivial scaling by an invariant scaling, then a consistent approach is given in Sec. 4.1 in [2].

9. *“Finally, a word on the papers [3] [☞](#), [4] [☞](#), [5] [☞](#), cited in [2] [Brethouwer’s Comment]. First, we would like to say again that our data is very much in line with all the relevant works of wall turbulence, including these ones. About the scaling laws therein, it is absolutely not our intent to belittle the achievements in these great papers but there a scale-induced curve-fit of the log-function for $\overline{u^2}$ is performed.”*

And what is done in [1]? If one is honest, then in [1] something very similar is done with the same degree of arbitrariness: Instead of a “scale-induced curve-fit”, an invariance-induced curve-fit of a power-function for the instantaneous moment $\overline{U_1^2}$ is performed, where, instead of a scale, two arbitrary invariances (8 and 9 in [1]) from an infinite pool of possible invariances were chosen to achieve this goal. That the proposed scaling approach in [1] is a first-principle method that directly leads to solutions is simply not true. The method in [1] is just another common trial-and-error method. But what makes it worse than any other scaling method proposed in the literature, is that it is possible to algebraically prove that the scaling in [1] leads to a non-removable inconsistency for the fluctuation moments, starting already as low as order $n = 2$, and which then systematically infects all higher orders with increasing intensity.

This is expressed as the matching failure shown by us in Fig. 1(c)-(d) in our Comment. While particularly in the log-layer for $n = 2$ appropriate tools from statistical data analysis are needed to detect this failure, the matching failure for the next higher order $n = 3$ is already so pronounced in this layer that no further analysis is needed. The reason for this failure lies in the fact that the two arbitrarily chosen invariances (8) and (9) are nonphysical in violating the classical principle of cause and effect (see [2] and the references therein). Discarding these invariances will improve the matching to the fluctuation moments by several orders of magnitude, as shown e.g. in Section 5 in [3], or Section 4 in [2], or as shown by Oberlack *et al.* themselves, e.g. in [11], which all is a further clear indication that these two statistical invariances in [1] are unphysical.

10. *“No equations in [3] [☞](#), [4] [☞](#), [5] [☞](#) are considered at all to which solutions, e.g. invariant solutions of the moment equations, are generated.”*

In [1] this also is not the case. It is aimed at, but not achieved. The instantaneous scaling laws derived in [1] are no solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations (see points 12-14 below).

Figure 4: Reproduction of Figure 2 in the Reply, including a change in the fitted parameter values by a tiny amount of 0.1%, showing that the fit of $\overline{u_1^2}$ in the log-law region is not natural and highly unstable. The circles show the DNS data of [1]. The solid black line is the best-fit according to the scaling law in the Reply, with the second-moment parameters ω , B_2 and C_2 . Their values are (to four significant digits): $\omega = 0.1087$, $B_2 = 524.9$, $C_2 = 482.4$ (κ and B are already preset by the first moment and given in [1]). Changing any of these second-moment parameters now by a tiny amount of 0.1%, either to $\omega = 0.1086$, $B_2 = 525.5$, $C_2 = 481.9$, results in each case in a large discrepancy, as shown by the red, blue and yellow curve, respectively. This unnatural high sensitivity against small perturbations in the fitting parameters of Oberlack’s symmetry-based scaling law to $\overline{u_1^2}$ is not special to channel flow. It has also already been demonstrated in zero-pressure-gradient (ZPG) turbulent boundary layer flow (see Fig. 4 in [3]). As proven therein, and reconfirmed again in [2] (see Secs. 4 & B.2), this problem is solved by discarding Oberlack’s nonphysical and thus non-realizable symmetries and replacing them by realizable ones, leading to structurally consistent invariant functions, which then show a natural and robust sensitivity to small perturbations.

11. “Moreover, in Fig. 2 we show the fitting to $\overline{u_1^2}^+$ with $\overline{u_{1fit}^2}^+ = C_2(y^+)^\omega - B_2 - (1/\kappa \ln(y^+) + B)^2$. ω and κ have the values obtained in [1], while C_2 and B_2 had to be slightly adjusted. It is clear that the fit is excellent, and this scaling law is a direct application of our theory.”

Firstly, what the authors do not reveal here is that although the Reynolds stress $\overline{u_1^2}$ in the log-layer can be fitted with their scaling law, it fits very unnaturally. Because, a quantity as $\overline{u_1^2}$, which varies in the fitted region of order 1, has to be fitted with parameters of order 100. The values of the shift and normalization parameters, B_2 and C_2 , are both around 400 to 500 and therefore not natural. This non-naturalness is particularly expressed by the fact that the resulting fit is not stable and therefore not robust. Already the smallest change in the parameter values leads to a large discrepancy, as shown in Fig. 4 above — for a more detailed discussion, including a sensitivity comparison to a structurally consistent invariant scaling law, see Sec. B.2 in [2].

Secondly, that with the results of [1] the Reynolds stress $\overline{u_1^2}$ in the log-layer can be fitted to the data, though very unnatural, is not the main problem here, since this fit is also shown in Fig. 1(d) in our Comment. The real problem is the fit of the next higher order $n = 3$, i.e. to $\overline{u_1^3}$, where an immense scaling error occurs, regardless of the fitting method used. Shown as the red line in our figure, this result clearly invalidates the symmetry-based scaling theory of Oberlack in [1]. But, as expected, this crucial issue is not addressed in the authors’ Reply. It is clear that attempts are being made here to ignore this inconvenient fact.

12. *“The first statement, i.e. ‘the scaling laws in [1] not solutions to the statistical Navier-Stokes equations’, where of course the higher moment equations are included, is obviously just nonsense. Anyone who knows a little about symmetries and turbulence will easily be able to show the invariance of the solution in the multi-point moment equation, rather similar to the Blasius solution in the boundary layer equation.”*

This statement is a clear misrepresentation of our critique. We do not object to the basic fact that the invariant functions derived in [1] will reduce the stationary 1-dimensional moment equations to an identity $0 = 0$ (up to some additional constraints in the group parameters that will be picked up in the process). Our objection is that in turbulence such a reduction is no guarantee that these invariant functions are then automatically solutions. This would be the case for laminar flow, where all dynamical equations are closed, but not in turbulence where they are unclosed. The problem is that for unclosed systems the strong concept of symmetry turns into the weaker concept of equivalence, where solutions are not necessarily mapped to solutions anymore. This very basic but crucial fact is being ignored by M. Oberlack for more than two decades now, which since then has led to all kinds of misleading and flawed results.

And Fig. 1(d) in our Comment clearly proves it, that the invariant functions in [1] are no solutions of the moment equations, since for $n \geq 3$ they cannot be matched to the data by any means whatsoever, and if, as for $n = 2$, then very unnaturally, as shown in Fig. 4 above. The inconsistency in the invariant functions, due to being based on two nonphysical and non-realizable invariances (8) and (9) in [1], already starts at $n = 2$, and then systematically infects all higher orders with increasing intensity, as explained already in point 9 above.

Finally note here that the authors again, as before, compare their case to the example of the Blasius solution in laminar boundary-layer flow. This is misleading and wrong. In Lie-group symmetry analysis the turbulent case cannot be compared with the laminar case, as was already pointed out in point 1 in the beginning.

13. *“Those who have ever run large-scale DNS and studied the resulting statistical turbulence data intensively know that different moments converge at different rates. ... The phenomenon criticized by Frewer is well known to anyone who has worked extensively with turbulence data”*

That $\overline{u_1^{n+1}}$ converges at a slower rate than $\overline{u_1^n}$ is something we are well aware of. At this point we did not criticize but only made aware the reader in Fig. 1(c) that particularly in channel center the DNS data at this stage cannot be used to test the instantaneous scaling laws in [1] beyond $n \geq 4$ when reformulating to the fluctuation moments.

It’s telling to see how the authors spend nearly half a page on something that is minor, but ignore all major problems of their study. Nothing is said about the severe mismatch shown by us through the red lines in Figs. 1(c)-(d), where the data of the corresponding moments $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ can be seen to be more or less converged, i.e., where structural changes are not to be expected anymore when the DNS continues to run. Convergence problems for $\overline{u_1^n}$ with structural changes still to occur, are, at this stage, only seen in channel center for $n \geq 4$, as shown in Fig. 1(c). However, the way the structures will change here will not be surprising and are trivial to predict: In Fig. 1(c) all moments will universally converge to a straight line with slope 2 close to channel center. This is the trivial universal aspect we explained in point 8 above.

14. “Given this background, the results shown in Frewer were known to us and are expected. If one aims alone to determine e.g. the second moment of U_1 -fluctuations ... one has only to make a slight modification of the parameters B_2 and C_2 in the equations (16) in [1]. This results in Fig. 2, which is obviously an extremely good fit for $\overline{u_1^2}$ ”

Despite the fact that their scaling to $\overline{u_1^2}$ in the log-layer fits very unnaturally, as explicitly demonstrated here in Fig. 4, such “a slight modification of the parameters” is not possible anymore for the next higher order $n = 3$, i.e. for $\overline{u_1^3}$, and also for all higher orders $n \geq 4$ in the log-layer. Even worse, they cannot be matched to the data at all anymore. It lies in the nature of things. For example, the scaling law for $\overline{u_1^3}$ in the log-layer

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overline{u_1^3}^+ &= C_3(y^+)^{2\omega} - B_3 - \left(\overline{U_1}^{+3} + 3\overline{U_1}^+ \overline{u_1^2}^+ \right), \\ \text{with } \overline{u_1^2}^+ &= C_2(y^+)^{\omega} - B_2 - \overline{U_1}^{+2}, \quad \overline{U_1}^+ = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln(y^+) + B, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

that results directly from the instantaneous scaling law (16) in [1] when reformulated to the equivalent representation of the fluctuation moments, will never fit the data of channel flow, regardless of how good the DNS data converged. It’s simply the inconsistent structure of (1.1) that makes all the problems, which for higher orders even gets worse. And this problem is not special to channel flow, but is also the case in zero-pressure-gradient (ZPG) turbulent boundary layer flow (see Fig. 5 in [3]). And the root for all these problems lies of course in the nonphysical and thus non-realizable “symmetries” (8) and (9) in [1]. In Section 4 in [2] we show how a *consistent* invariance-based structure for the fluctuation moments $\overline{u_1^n}$ may look like.

2. Crucial points of critique that were not addressed in the Reply

In our Comment there are four points that invalidate the symmetry-based scaling approach in [1], but which the authors systematically ignored and did not comment on in their Reply. Sorted by relevance, these are:

1. The red line shown in Fig. 1(d). This proves that their scaling law for the third fluctuation moment $\overline{u_1^3}$ in the log-layer cannot be matched to the data, and that this problem is structural and not a convergence issue of the data or a numerical stability issue of the fitting procedure. Since in the space of all norm functions no better fit can be generated and since this problem continues for all higher orders, this severe mismatch proves that in the log-layer the scaling laws in [1] are not solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations, as is incorrectly claimed therein.

2. The red line shown in Fig. 1(c). This proves that their scaling law for the second fluctuation moment $\overline{u_1^2}$ in channel center cannot be matched to the data, and, as before, is again a structural problem and not a convergence issue of the data or a numerical stability issue of the fitting procedure. Since again in the space of all norm functions no better fit can be generated, this mismatch proves that in [1] the scaling law for the Reynolds-stress $\overline{u_1^2}$ in channel center is not a solution of the Navier-Stokes equations.

3. The perfect fit of the *turbulent* scaling law (19-20) in [1] to the data of *laminar* flow in channel center, as shown in Fig. 1(a). This proves several things. First, the structure of parallel lines is not due to a special turbulent flow property, but is a trivial universal aspect that can be achieved with any moment function that is not zero in channel center (see again the detailed explanation in point 8 of the previous section). Therefore, secondly, that this feature should reflect the intermittent behaviour of turbulent channel flow, as claimed in [1], is not true. And thirdly, a sophisticated scaling theory is not needed to predict the slope of these parallel lines. It's just the exponent of the first non-zero Taylor-expansion term around channel center.

4. The perfect fit of the instantaneous moments to the data by just using two fitting parameters instead of seven, as shown in Fig. 1(b). This proves that the higher order scaling laws in [1] are not needed to predict the scaling behaviour of the *instantaneous* moments. And, to use them to predict the scaling behaviour of the corresponding fluctuation moments, fails, as shown in Fig. 1(c)-(d), since they ultimately are not solutions to the Navier-Stokes equations.

In other words, the “perfect” match to the instantaneous moments as shown in [1] is misleading and does not lead to a correct prediction of turbulent scaling beyond the mean flow. What we see here is just the coarse structure of the mean flow and its various powers, which ultimately constitutes only a trivial result once the scaling of the fitted mean field is known, as shown in our Comment in Fig. 1(b), while all the fine structure characterizing turbulence cannot be predicted, as shown in Fig. 1(c)-(d).

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